

VALIDATION OF THE “SLADECOM” MODEL AS A CONTEMPORARY PANACEA FOR THE IMPROVEMENT OF FORMAL LAND MARKET IN NIGERIA

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Abstract:

Land has been variously acknowledged as a perennial harbinger of socio-economic power that exudes prestige and class. It is the foundation for food and shelter, driving the very bedrock that significantly provides for most employment opportunities in the country side. Regrettably, as global urbanisation trends soars uncontrollably, land is rapidly becoming increasingly scarce assets in cities. Therefore, supplying of and demand for lands, especially within urban spheres, are though unfortunately never at equilibrium, but the present scenarios in formal window of urban land market, which is solely responsible for the supply of formal land for various developmental purposes, has been very unimpressive. This simply, has rendered delivery to be at its lowest ebb, such that accessibility, which is the measure of demand coefficients from the part of the various land users, to be hampered, the resultant effects of which is consistent decrease of the real estate stock. Hence, it is in astounding recognition of the above ugly scenario that this study was conducted, primarily to validate the potentialities of SLADECOM model which is an end product of a doctoral research. Essentially, this model is meant to remove all the established barriers that are rendering the supply side (i.e delivery) as well as the demand side (i.e accessibility) of the formal market for urban lands, so sub-

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optimal. Moreover, the following constructs and variables that survived the statistical screening exercise were coined as components of this Sladecom model for empirical validation, such as: structural and culturo-behavioural dynamics (scbd), socio-political and economic dictates (sped), human techno-analytical arsenals (htaa), policy relevance and appropriateness (pra), contents and context of policies (ccp) and role mediation regime (rnr). Furthermore, validation, which is unlike just any other survey, requires high level of integrity, as results from it are almost laws in their plausibility, which simply suggests that respondents with huge experience, towering knowledge and consummate understanding of the issues involved in the subject matter are carefully selected for data collection. Out of the rough total of over 500 individuals considered as the total population for the sample space, 205 individuals qualified for the sample frame, from which the sample size of 120 was chosen, upon which the structured questionnaires were distributed. Therefore, after necessary integrity checks, 92 out 107 questionnaires that were retrieved, were found to be valid, thus formed the denominator for the analyses, using 5 point Likert scale of measurement, corroborated with pie-charts for stronger inferential and descriptive statistical results and explanations. The findings amongst other things are that this model has great potential to drastically reduce multiple roles partitioning among formal land administration machineries and thus increases the speed, quality and quantity of service delivery to prospective teeming land users. Among the recommendations is that decisive actions must be expeditiously taken on generating more functional databases and also increase the frequency of contents updating of these databases. This will no doubt improve the technical prowess of formal land administration machineries, with resultant capability to address myriad of challenges of formal land delivery and accessibility in Nigeria.

JEL: R14, R52, R31

Keywords: validation, SLADECOR model, contemporary panacea, formal land market improvement, Nigeria

1. Introduction

Nigeria is widely known to be of rapidly trending demographic bursts, manifesting in almost unprecedented urbanisation and population growth among the nations of the world (Oderinde, 2008). The indices of her rate of population growth fluctuate between (36 and 40) %, with citizens within the bracket of urban poverty classification ranging between (40 and 45) % among various categories of city dwellers (FOS, 2012). Needless

to say that, housing and by extension land upon where to build the house, ranks very high among the basic things that man longs for and strives to get, within the cities in Nigeria, as the case globally. It is then apparent, that supply of land is consistently being outpaced by demand for land, for which land market should be constantly enriched with novel ideas and methodology, in being far ahead of the seemingly endless spiral of the demand-supply dichotomous challenges, among several other problems confronting formal delivery and accessibility of urban lands for residential and other types of land use developments. Especially, as it has become such a notoriety among city dwellers, that land is almost only being seen as an hallmark to measure richness and classic social status, hence, this tends to spice up the propensity of average city dweller to devise all mechanisms, in amassing stupendous size of land parcels to himself, be it through invasion, grabbing, legal purchase, legitimate sale and even outright stealing, so as to reap the unending benefits of ownership (Fabiya, 1990; Akinbola et al., 2015a).

Furthermore, it is noteworthy that past researchers and scholars on the cities in Nigeria and entire Africa, Asia and Pacific Island had confessed that they were amazed with litany of challenges associated with delivery and accessibility of developable lands, for various developmental purposes, especially for urban residential development. Such problems manifest in the dimensions of formal market being shrouded in contingently spiralled scenarios, excessively unwarranted cost, corruption, extremely prolonged delay; deliberately belated litigations among others, such that the emerging cycles had perennially outpriced formal residential lands beyond the affordability of the poor city dwellers, ostensibly denying the sectoral component that forms the majority of the Nigeria's population (UNESCAP, 2000; Omirin, 2003; Rakodi and Leduka, 2003; Aluko and Amidu, 2006, Akinbola et al, 2015a, Akinbola and Md Yassin, 2016b).

Therefore, it is within the purveying of the above reflections, that this research was conducted, essentially to validate the overall result, that is, the potentialities of the SLADECOM model, that was evolved as an end product of the doctoral in-depth study, that was carried out to unravel the several challenges bedeviling the formal delivery and accessibility of urban lands in Nigeria, with a view to proffering lasting solutions to these challenges.

2. Literature Review and Conceptual Clarifications

More salient in sub-Saharan Africa is the fact that land tenure administration has been dominated by customary institutional structures of authority that predate the modern

state (Bruce, 1998b; Herbst, 2000; World Bank, 2003a). The area of land under formal legal tenure covers only between 2 and 10 percent of total land (World Bank 2003a). In the West African region as a whole, it is estimated that only 2 – 3% of land is covered by formal legal documentation (Toulmin, 2008). The percentage of land covered by formal tenure registration in the form of legal title in countries like Nigeria and Ghana is estimated to be 20%, in Burundi it is estimated to be only 1% (Toulmin, 2008). There is a sort of agreement among scholars that the dominance of customary tenure is due to the chequered path of state formation through the pre-colonial, colonial, and postcolonial periods (Bruce, 1998b; Dia, 1996; Donald, 1996; Herbst, 2000; Mamdani, 1996; Ray, 1999). However, the crucial challenge that has faced many scholars and policy makers concerns how to reform the dominant customary estate controlled by traditional authorities. Hence, drawing from the general land policy and tenure situation across western, eastern and southern countries in Africa, it is clear that customary institutional structures of power dominate land administration in African countries.

Furthermore, the indigenous institutions of land administration in the numerous pre-colonial traditional states in Africa, together with their political structures of authority, were largely left intact by the colonial state established by European countries. The indigenous institutional foundations of the pre-colonial state were legitimated through long-held cultural values and wars of conquest. The modern state in Africa therefore inherited the colonial state, with its dominant customary land tenure institutions, through shallow democratic processes (Quan et al, 2004). The official land tenure policies in African countries paint an interesting picture about the contentious internal land politics and the powerful influence of customary authorities on the state. As of 1996, it was only a handful of countries such as Eritrea, Ethiopia, Mozambique and Zambia that had legally asserted state ownership of the land as official tenure policy. While western scholars and some African political elites may assert that the state is the ultimate landowner; many governments hesitate to wield the same discourse in their domestic land politics. The internal politics over tenure policy has undoubtedly affected this institutional reform process of legal formalization (Bandeira et al, 2010).

In reality, formal land tenure policy in the modern African state is usually a reflection of the inherited formal structures of power at the top-level of government, and the indigenous informal customary structures of authority that dominate land administration in local communities. The emerging land tenure policy in Africa simultaneously integrates both the formal and customary institutional structures of power into the state (World Bank, 2003a). Consequently, the power of the modern democratic state to formally assert a coercive monopoly over land administration is effectively blunted by its underlying heterogeneous institutional structures. The large

area of land covered by informal or customary institutions of land tenure has been the primary focus of recent legal formalization programmes by national governments and international policy actor (Herbst, 2000s).

Interestingly, existing conceptions of legal formalization of land tenure in Africa are grounded in the western conception of the state as "ultimate landowner" (Quan et al, 2004). Scholars and practitioners concerned with Land in Africa joined African politicians at a conference convened in London to grasp the nettle of real-politique and redefine the African state as ultimate landowner (Quan et al, 2004). From this western European perspective, the conference participants argued: "*The accumulation of land and power over it by the state itself represents an alienation of rights of landholding groups, which merits either restitution or compensation*". While the notion of the state as ultimate landowner is asserted against rival customary claims, the specific character of the internal politics of the modern state is fatally ignored. This new discourse being wielded in European capitals is however not consistent with the general land policy situation in many African countries where governments explicitly recognize customary land tenure as deriving from indigenous institutional structures of power rather than the modern state. In other words, in spite of the powerful chorus about the African state as "ultimate landowner", what is being sung by scholars and African politicians in European capitals, is that, the internal reality of tenure conflicts and policy uncertainty have cast their shadows over the appropriate conceptualization of the ownership and nature of the 'customary'.

Atwood (1990) sees land titling or registration, in the African context, as being referred to as a legally sanctioning primary land claims which are already recognized informally by the local community (although they may have been previously ignored or denied in formal law). It involves taking these claims out of the realm of informal lineage or community land ownership and making them fully legal, formal and individual; measuring precisely the boundaries of each claim; recording claims in a formal, state-administered land records system; and, under the Torrens system of title, providing a state guarantee to the claim that appears in the land records system. This conventional land tenure institutional reform implies that any previous informal claims held by traditional authorities, rulers, chiefs, or kingdoms over land ownership is declared void by the state and then defined as derived from grants made by the state. In reality, however, many African states jointly share land ownership rights with the dominant customary institutional structures of power.

Formal land market is likened to a process that involves the regulation of the use, conversion and development of land, collection of revenues from the sales, taxation and leasing of land, as well as resolution of ownership and land use problems (Dale and

McLaughlin (1999). Several activities which should be involved in land administration along with several issues in land rights were hereby summarised. Meanwhile, this definition differentiates between the land information system and the broader land administration system (Bandeira et al, 2010; Molen, 2002), it was further argued that management of land right system is similar to land administration, except for few scholars with dissenting views on this definition (Lindsay, 2002; and Li et al., 2009). This definition is more encompassing than those that preceded it, as it describes land administration as synonymous to formal land market, which involves a combination of institutions, policies, processes and procedures in the management of land rights systems.

This system involves the delimitation of boundaries of land, planning and control of the use of land, the allocation of land, valuation and taxation of land, the collection and recording of information about land and transactions and involvement in resolutions of uncertainties over ownership and boundaries of land (Li et al, 2009). Another definition of land administration, which is in the complexion of China's design, sees it as a process that involves the organisation, coordination, supervision and management of land, including resources, use, property rights, and profit by institutions set up for society (Li et. al, 2009). An infrastructure of the formal land market, which is analogous to formal land administration infrastructure, is defined as the policy instruments, legal frameworks, institutional design, and technical tools that underpin the delivery of these four functions (Bennett et al., 2012). In discussing definitions of land administration, some researchers disagree over the distinction between land administration and the management of land. For instance, Karika et al. (2003) classify land use and land development as part of land management and restrict information about ownership and taxation to land administration activities only.

Finally, it is being consciously appreciated within the context of this study, that for accessibility to be smoothly achieved, it must be married to socio-political and economic standpoints of government, which operationalised via her numerous policies, one of which touches aspect of delivery. However, to realise this simple chemistry, consideration must be duly given to past, present and likely emerging land tenure systems. Legally and / or customarily defined stances on land tenure, sees it as the relationship, whether, amongst people, as individuals or groups, with respect to land (FAO, 2010, Akinbola and Md Yassin, 2016b). Therefore, it is with clear appreciation of the centrality of the simple assertion above to land delivery and accessibility, together with such other factors like momentous econo-demographic indices and their ugliness, which had manifested in seemingly endless exponentially unbridled challenges, which had led to the evolvement of a robust model, called SLADECOM, as contained in figure

1, showing the intricate communication among its several components, in terms of their statistical significant and relevance of their individual and collective impacts on the overall issues of formal delivery and accessibility of urban lands in Nigeria, through the validation of its potentialities to address these negative impacts, the rationale for which this study was convoked.

Figure 1: SLADECOM Model (Akinbola, 2017)

3. Materials and Method

Out of the rough total of over 500 individuals considered as the total population for the sample space, 205 individuals qualified for the sample frame, from which the sample size of 120 was chosen, upon which the structured questionnaires consisting of 23 mentally stimulating questions that are subsumed into 6 constructs around which the components of the SLADECOM model that was evolved from the doctoral research were conveniently situated and revolved. Strictly, because of the integrity expected of a validation exercise, distribution of questionnaires for data collection was among chief estate or land / town planning / surveying / magistrate officers and above in relevant core MDAs, veterans in the appropriate regulatory capacities, senior lecturers and above in the departments of real estate, urban and regional planning, land surveying and law among universities and polytechnics, as well as principal and managing partners plus directors of consultancies and NGOs with mandates on land and shelter issues, and finally very handful land users and developers with very enviable experience and knowledge of land related issues, all within the six states of the south-western Nigeria.

Therefore, using simple convenience mixed with purposive sampling, so as to achieve a fair, balanced and unbiased research outcome from these creams of opposing sets of respondents, from which primary data were collected, after necessary integrity checks, 92 out 107 questionnaires that were retrieved, were found to be valid, thus formed the denominator for the analyses, using 5 point Likert scale of measurement, corroborated with pie-charts for stronger inferential and descriptive statistical results and explanations, from where logical inferences were drawn for the final interpretation of the research findings.

4. Data Analyses

The table 1 below sheds light on some of the responses of the stakeholders, as distilled from the returned questionnaires for analyses, with the application of average of the responses from the varying determinant statements of each of the measuring parameters, to draw necessary inferences and judgement from the data displayed on the tables, thus:

S/N		Constructs / Responses From career land officers in the MDAs, NGOs, Academicians, Independent Land Consultants and Various Categories of Land Users/ Developers.				
		SD	D	U	A	SA
1.		Structural and Culturo-Behavioural Dynamics :				
	P ₁ R _{MS}	(8) 8.69%	(10) 10.87%	(3) 3.26%	(43) 6.74%	(28) 30.44%
2		Socio-Political and Economic Dictates				
	P ₂ R _{MS}	(8) 8.69%	(11) 11.95%	(2) 2.17%	(43) 46.74%	(28) 30.44%
3		Human-Techno Analytical Arsenal				
	P ₃ R _{MS}	(8) 8.69%	(9) 9.78%	(3) 3.26%	(42) 45.65%	(30) 32.61%
4		Policy Relevance and Appropriateness				
	P ₄ R _{MS}	(7) 7.61%	(11) 11.95%	(3) 3.26%	(43) 46.74%	(28) 30.44%
5.		Contents and Context of Policies				
	P ₅ R _{MS}	(9) 9.78%	(10) 10.87%	(2) 2.17%	(41) 44.57%	(30) 32.61%
6		Role Mediation Regime				
	P ₆ R _{MS}	(7) 7.61%	(9) 9.78%	(3) 3.26%	(43) 46.74%	(30) 32.61%

5. Results and Discussion

Table 1 above clearly shows the following as interpretations of the cumulative averages of 23 items of questions distilled from all the six parameters that were coined into constructs, against which the SLADECOM model was being measured for validation, thus:

5.1 Validation Rating of the Potentials of SLADECOM Model on Structural and Culturo-Behavioural Dynamics and Overall Impacts on Formal Delivery and Accessibility of Urban Lands

Responses to the first SLADECOM parameter (i.e Structural and culturo-behavioural dynamics) which were calibrated and measured in mean score on table1 are further expressed on percentile scale chart (see figure 2). It clearly validates that SLADECOM model has the potential to increase speed, quantity and quality of service as well improve the operational interrelationships with overall impact on formal land delivery and accessibility, with average of 43 respondents (46.74%) agreeing and average of 28 respondents (30.44%) strongly agreeing, while just 8 respondents (8.69%), 10 respondents (10.87%) and 3 respondents (3.26%) strongly disagree, disagree and

undecided respectively on the validation of the positive impacts of SLADECOM on the improvement of formal land market in Nigeria.

5.2 Validation Rating of the Potentials of SLADECOM Model on Socio-Political and Economic Dictates and Overall Impacts on Formal Delivery and Accessibility of Urban Lands

Responses to the second SLADECOM parameter (i.e Socio-political and economic dictates) which were calibrated and measured in mean score on table1 are further expressed on percentile scale chart (see figure 3). It clearly validates that SLADECOM model has the potential to remove trauma of total loss reduces development costs and time, removes uncertainties and concretises actions, with overall impact on formal land delivery and accessibility in Nigeria, with average of 43 respondents (46.74%) agreeing and average of 28 respondents (30.44%) strongly agreeing, while just 8 respondents (8.69%), 11 respondents (11.95%) and 2 respondents (2.17%) strongly disagree, disagree and undecided respectively on the validation of the positive impacts of SLADECOM on the improvement of formal land market in Nigeria.

5.3 Validation Rating of the Potentials of SLADECOM Model on Human Techno-Analytical Arsenal and Overall Impacts on Formal Delivery and Accessibility of Urban Lands

Responses to the third SLADECOM parameter (i.e Human techno-analytical arsenal) which were calibrated and measured in mean score on table1 are further expressed on percentile scale chart (see figure 4). It clearly validates that SLADECOM model has the potential to buoy workforce with sophistication and technical vigour, enhances seamless facilitation and extension of knowledge and promotes sharing of technological know-how with highest possible mastery, with average of 42 respondents (45.65%) agreeing and average of 30 respondents (32.61%) strongly agreeing, while just 8 respondents (8.69%), 9 respondents (9.78%) and 3 respondents (3.26%) strongly disagree, disagree and undecided respectively on the validation of the positive impacts of SLADECOM on the improvement of formal land market in Nigeria

5.4 Validation Rating of the Potentials of SLADECOM Model on Policy Relevance and Appropriateness and Overall Impacts on Formal Delivery and Accessibility of Urban Lands

Responses to the fourth SLADECOM parameter (i.e Policy relevance and appropriateness) which were calibrated and measured in mean score on table1 are further expressed on percentile scale chart (see figure 5). It clearly validates that SLADECOM model has the potential to, harmonise all existing incongruous policies and straighten them for greater relevance and applicability, also offers platform to synergise effectively among the machineries of land delivery, so as to buy them for superb performance, with average of 43 respondents (46.74%) agreeing and average of 28 respondents (30.44%) strongly agreeing, while just 7 respondents (7.61%), 11 respondents (11.95%) and 3 respondents (3.26%) strongly disagree, disagree and undecided respectively on the validation of the positive impacts of SLADECOM on the improvement of formal land market in Nigeria.

5.5 Validation Rating of the Potentials of SLADECOM Model on Contents and Context of Policies and Overall Impacts on Formal Delivery and Accessibility of Urban Lands

Responses to the fifth SLADECOM parameter (i.e Contents and context of policies) which were calibrated and measured in mean score on table1 are further expressed on percentile scale chart (see figure 6). It clearly validates that SLADECOM model has the potential to truly demystify some of the peculiarities inherent in formal land delivery and accessibility via the "nigerianisation" of the policies, as well as incorporating sanctionable measures to curb unwholesomeness of any guise, which ultimately will transform formal land market for enviable turn-around in all ramifications, with average of 41 respondents (44.57%) agreeing and average of 30 respondents (32.61%) strongly agreeing, while just 9 respondents (9.78%), 10 respondents (10.87%) and 2 respondents (2.17%) strongly disagree, disagree and undecided respectively on the validation of the positive impacts of SLADECOM on the improvement of formal land market in Nigeria

5.6 Validation Rating of the Potentials of SLADECOM Model on Role Mediation Regime and Overall Impacts on Formal Delivery and Accessibility of Urban Lands

Responses to the sixth parameter (i.e Role mediation regime) which were calibrated and measured in mean score on table1 are further expressed on percentile scale chart (see figure 7). It clearly validates that SLADECOM model has the potential to frontally remove possible misconceptions and lessen the associated burdensomeness of the complex tasks formal land delivery, as well as timely revealing areas that are constantly being exploited by unscrupulous actors for monitoring and possible checkmating. All these ultimately improves delivery and increases accessibility, with average of 43 respondents (46.74%) agreeing and average of 30 respondents (32.61%) strongly agreeing, while just 7 respondents (7.61%), 9 respondents (9.78%) and 3 respondents (3.26%) strongly disagree, disagree and undecided respectively on the validation of the positive impacts of SLADECOM on the improvement of formal land market in Nigeria

6. Summary of Findings, Conclusion and Recommendation

6.1 Summary of Findings

1. Analysis of the first component of SLADECOM model, which doubles as the first measuring parameter, that is, structural and culturo-behavioural dynamics, shows very incontrovertibly clear that the model of SLADECOM has the much desirable potential to increase speed, quantity and quality of service as well improve the operational interrelationships among machineries, with overall impact on formal land delivery and accessibility
2. Analysis of the second component of SLADECOM model, which doubles as the second measuring parameter, that is, socio-political and economic dictates, shows convincingly clear that the model of SLADECOM has the much desirable potential to remove trauma of total loss, reduces development costs and time,

removes uncertainties and concretises actions, with overall impact on formal land delivery and accessibility in Nigeria

3. Analysis of the third component of SLADECOM model, which doubles as the third measuring parameter, that is, human techno-analytical arsenal, shows very glaringly copious that the model of SLADECOM has the much astounding potential to buoy workforce with sophistication and technical vigour, enhances seamless facilitation and extension of knowledge and promotes sharing of technological know-how, with overall impact on formal land delivery and accessibility in Nigeria.
4. Analysis of the fourth component of SLADECOM model, which doubles as the fourth measuring parameter, that is, policy relevance and appropriateness, shows very reassuringly clear that the model of SLADECOM has the much beneficial potential to harmonise all the existing incongruous policies and inconsistent provisions and straighten them for greater relevance and applicability, also offers platform to synergise effectively among the machineries of land delivery, so as to buoy them for superb performance, with overall impact on formal land delivery and accessibility in Nigeria.
5. Analysis of the fifth component of SLADECOM model, which doubles as the fifth measuring parameter, that is, contents and context of policies, shows very unambiguously clear that the model of SLADECOM has the much impactful potential to truly demystify some of the peculiarities inherent in formal land delivery and accessibility via the "nigerianisation" of the policies, as well as incorporating sanctionable measures to curb unwholesomeness of any guise from all stakeholders, which ultimately will transform formal land market for enviable turn-around in all ramifications, with overall impact on formal land delivery and accessibility in Nigeria.
6. Analysis of the sixth component of SLADECOM model, which doubles as the sixth measuring parameter, that is, role mediation regime, shows very undoubtedly clear that the model of SLADECOM has much rewarding potential to frontally remove possible misconceptions and lessen the associated burdensomeness of the complex tasks inherent in formal land delivery, as well as timely revealing areas that are constantly being exploited by unscrupulous actors for monitoring and possible checkmating., with overall impact on formal land delivery and accessibility in Nigeria.

6.2 Conclusion

It is noteworthy that, the present ugly scenarios, as obtained in the formal land market in Nigeria, are as a result of several of the problems bedevilling the formal land delivery machineries, encapsulating administration, management, control and regulation/policy, with the resultant negative impacts on formal land accessibility, as being faced as ultimate challenges by several categories of land users and developers. All these issues, notwithstanding, the contemporariness of the robust potentials subsumed into building the SLADECOM model, makes the model so novel and enduring, in addressing all of these challenges with which formal land market in Nigeria is plagued at moment, even decades to come.

6.3 Recommendations

1. Re-ordering of the lop-sidedness in the interrelationship among land administrators and regulators.
2. Attach competitive packages to increased workload and goal attainment land agencies' officials, e.g double promotion, salary increase, etc
3. Increased budgetary allocation to really make land as a consociate capital and not entirely economic good, until it latently becomes source of wealth
4. Actual physical and considerable increase in staff strength (quantity and quality).
5. Evolving a platform to vantagely involve veterans to consistently mentor career land officials
6. All land policies' inconsistencies must be harmonised and common areas must be strengthened to invigorate them for better applicability and enliven them for greater relevance
7. Vigorous increase in the level of visibility on monitoring of land development compliance as enshrined in policies
8. Incorporation of the voice of all stakeholders involved in entire formal land delivery and accessibility spectrum

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